

HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT AND PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES OF THE TEACHER OF MUSIC

Pirnazarov Laziz Kakhramonovich

Teacher at Karshi State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7957982>

Abstract. *Issues are considered in all spheres of “art of pedagogy” at all its levels, there is a search for more advanced forms and methods of teaching, corresponding to the requirements of the time, capable of providing a solution to the problems that faced the country on the threshold of the third millennium.*

Keywords: *music, teacher, education, training, pedagogy, psychology, history, development, music.*

It is no exception and that its specific branch, which is associated with the teaching of musical disciplines. And here, intensive research is underway on more effective methods and methods of educational work with students, attempts are being made to introduce theoretical and practical innovations into the activities of musician teachers. . Serious achievements were marked in the last two or three decades by the scientific and practical efforts of leading domestic specialists who developed the problems of organizing the teaching of music, the content, forms and methods of educational work; problems of expanding and enriching the spiritual and general cultural potential of student musicians; problems of psychological and pedagogical properties.

Meanwhile, some fundamentally significant issues, on the solution of which the improvement of the state of Russian musical pedagogy depends, remained outside the field of view of specialists. These include, in particular, issues of the formation of individual and professional qualities of a music teacher in their internal systemic relationships and dependencies. How is the internal balance of these qualities and properties determined and expressed? What personal and professional parameters play a priority role in this case? How do the requirements of the profession affect the crystallization of individual personal qualities and properties of a music teacher, and, on the other hand, which of these qualities and properties specifically create conditions for “maximum favorable conditions” for engaging in the corresponding activity?

It should be emphasized that the author of the study does not aim to consider ALL types and methods of activity of a teacher-musician and, accordingly, the personal and professional qualities (properties) of a specialist in this profile due to them. It would hardly be possible within the framework of one work, because the hierarchy and quantitative and qualitative composition of these properties are so diverse, and the elements that form this complex are marked by such diversity, mobility, diversity, etc., that it is unlikely that all this would be able to succumb to strict scientific accounting and systematization. In addition, it is not always possible to draw clear demarcation lines between the professionally significant qualities and properties of a music teacher - and his colleagues representing other academic disciplines. There are other difficulties that arise when attempting a comprehensive, "global" solution to the problem of such problems.

To identify especially favorable conditions for the formation of attributive qualities and properties of a music teacher in the process of professional training in the conductor-choir class; to understand in the course of theoretical and scientific-practical analysis - why and for what reasons this happens "

1. Determine the pedagogical foundations for the formation and development of professionally significant qualities and properties of a music teacher in the course of his special training.

2. Check the put forward theoretical and methodological provisions in the corresponding experimental work.

The **METHODOLOGICAL BASIS** of the study were the works of didacticians and psychologists devoted to various aspects of the problem of forming professionally significant qualities of a teacher. An important place in the methodological foundation of the dissertation belongs to provisions that reflect integral trends in the psychological and pedagogical training of teachers (O.A. Abdullina, V.A.Isaev, A.T.Mishchenko, V.A.Slastenin, A.I.Shcherbakov).

The author relied simultaneously on the theory of professional orientation and the concept of professional self-determination in pedagogy and psychology, which is close to it in a number of areas / P.P.Blonsky, A.E.Golomshgok, I.D.Zvereva, E.A. Klimov, I.N.Nazimov, V.A.Polyakov, S.N.Chistyakova, S.T.Shatsky and others. With varying degrees of completeness and from different angles, issues related to the professional qualities and properties of music teachers are treated in the works of E.B.Abdullina, Yu.B.Alieva, L.G.Archazhnikova, T.N.Baklanova and Mutsmakhera, L.A.Rapatskaya and others; these works, of course, were taken into account by the dissertator. Creatively interpreted in the course of research and work of a psycho-pedagogical nature, belonging to musicians. T.M.Kogan, T.A. Kolysheva, A.I.Malyukov, V.I.Petrushin, G.M.Tsy-pin and others. The works of domestic choirmasters T.N.Baturinskaya, V.L.Zhivov, S.A.Kazachkov, K.F. Nikolskaya-Beregovskaya, V.I. Safonov and specialists in the field of vocals V.P.Morozov, G.P.Stulova, L.V.Shamin.

In the course of this study, such **METHODS** were used as a theoretical analysis of special literature / pedagogy, psychology, methods of musical education and upbringing, musicology; generalization of pedagogical experience; critical analysis and scientific and practical interpretation of the personal experience of the dissertation author; purposeful observation of students of choral classes of higher musical educational institutions; pedagogical questioning, interview, testing, interviewing, as well as a training / formative / experiment.

The figure of the teacher, his social status and functions* for centuries have been the subject of attention of the best minds of mankind.

Scientists attribute the period of emergence of pedagogical knowledge to the times of ancient times. It is due to the need to transfer the accumulated experience, labor skills and abilities. The functions of mentors in primitive society were performed by the elders of the clan - the most respected and experienced people.

Interest in the problem of the teacher began to form in antiquity, in the era when educational institutions first appeared, and the issues of education and future citizens became a matter of national importance. Judging by the data of special studies, the era of antiquity put forward rather high demands on the teacher. In ancient Greece, the most authoritative, talented civilians most often became teachers. In ancient Rome, state officials were appointed as teachers on behalf of the emperor, who knew well the sciences, culture and customs of different peoples, who spoke languages.

In the states of the Ancient East (Babylon, Egypt, Syria), teachers were priests who were considered the chosen ones of the Gods and were a privileged caste. In Ancient China, the so-

called ministry, which was in charge of the affairs of enlightenment of the people, appointed the most worthy representatives of society to the post of teacher.

With the development of social relations, it became necessary to generalize knowledge and experience in the field of upbringing and education of young people. This need has influenced the development of pedagogical science. Initially, it was an integral part of philosophy; many interesting pedagogical thoughts and statements belonged to its representatives.

Ancient Greek thinkers such as Democritus, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, despite the difference in philosophical positions, were united in understanding the importance of the role of the teacher in the life of society. Plato first put forward the idea that the upbringing of the younger generation should be the prerogative of the state. He believed that such a public position as a teacher, “consisting of all kinds of care in the education of boys and girls”, is much more significant than the highest positions in the state”.

Actively engaged in pedagogical activity, many ancient Greek philosophers were filled with the consciousness of the high significance of their teaching mission and considered their duties in this area more important than the duties of parents (Socrates, Plato). Sometimes even thoughts were expressed about eliminating the family from the process of education.

In the Middle Ages, the management of education in European countries passed from the state to the church. Priests, monks, clerks, as a rule, became teachers, in city schools - hired artisans and merchants, among whom there were many illiterate people. The higher clergy treated the enlightenment of the people with disdain, and therefore the requirements for the teacher were low. In later times (X-XI centuries), with the advent of universities, people with special education began to meet more often.

A particular surge of interest in the problem of the personality of a teacher is observed in the Renaissance, a period * when the humanistic ideas of ancient times are revived and find their development, the ideals of harmony and beauty of a person are renewed. The ascetic postulates of the Middle Ages are free in their thoughts and feelings of a person.

Humanist educators, condemning the teacher’s authoritarianism, characteristic of the pedagogy of the Middle Ages, demanded an attentive attitude towards the child, respect for his personality. Hence the close interest in the question of the moral character of the mentor. Thus, the representative of the humanistic trend in European culture of the XVI-XVII centuries, Erasmus Rotterdam, in his pedagogical views, advocated the high moral qualities of a teacher, such as love for children, patience, friendliness, benevolence, integrity, thanks to which the teacher will gain the love of pupils - the basis of successful learning. “The first step on the path of education,” E. Rotterdamsky emphasized, “is attachment to his mentor, a child who, first of all, loves classes thanks to his teacher, will eventually fall in love with the teacher” (5). The 11th century is the century of the birth and development of new socio-cultural and economic relations. The formation of the social system has an impact on the development of science and technology. In this regard, the requirements for the general level of knowledge are increasing, there is a need to train professionally competent specialists in the field of education with a wide range of knowledge, learning abilities, armed with special methods. This social order could not but affect pedagogical views. By the XI century, the need arose to create a special branch of knowledge - pedagogy

The foundations of the pedagogy of the new time were laid in the works of Jan Amos Comenius for the first time put forward special requirements for educational activities. These

qualities, according to I.A.Comenius, stem from the knowledge of the principles of training and education, firstly, and the possession of methods of educational work, secondly.

Of interest are the statements of Y.A.Comenius about what a teacher should be: “If teachers are friendly and affectionate, they will not repel children from themselves with their harsh treatment, but will attract them with their paternal disposition, manners and words; if teachers recommend the sciences, to which they buy from the side of excellence, attractiveness and lightness, if more diligent students are praised from time to time, if teachers treat students with love, then they will easily win their hearts so that it will be more pleasant to be at school than at home” (54, 342). A vivid portrait of the “ideal” educator was given by the great French thinker J.J.Rousseau. In his pedagogical judgments, the idea is that the teacher should study and take into account the natural inclinations and inclinations of children, as well as their age characteristics, in order to educate a free, independent person, a representative of a new society, F, F, Rousseau opposed harsh discipline, corporal punishment, i.e. against such relations to the child, which would suppress his personality.

However, putting forward the idea of “natural” education, J.J. Rousseau did not fully appreciate the role of the teacher, giving priority to the independent, free development of the child. For Rousseau, the teacher is “only a watchman and protector of the child from spoilage and bad influences” (25,358).

A great contribution to the development of foreign pedagogical thought in the XIX century was made by such prominent representatives of democratic pedagogy as I.G.Pestalozzi and F.W.A. Diesterweg.

Developing the ideas of Comenius, the outstanding Swiss teacher I.G. Pestalozzi, himself being an example of high morality, attached great importance to the individual and personal qualities of the teacher. The teacher, in his vision, is the educator of children’s souls, the “kindergartener”, “... a person full of love, wisdom, with an innocent soul, appreciating love, order and self-control”. On the professional side, this is a person “capable of seeing with a comprehensive eye what a child should become in the future”, i.e. possessing pedagogical foresight, Such a teacher, according to I.G.Pestalozzi is able to “.. raise the youth to a new way of thinking” (98, 461). For the first time clearly and clearly the requirements for a teacher, for those qualities that he must possess, were formulated by A.Diesterweg, one of the most prominent German figures in progressive bourgeois-democratic pedagogy. His approaches to this problem are reflected in his global work - "A Guide to the Education of German Teachers".

The leading quality of a teacher, according to A.Diesterweg, is love for his profession, which reveals itself in love for his subject, his students, as well as in the desire to be a comprehensively educated person.

Considering the teacher the leading figure in the learning process, A. Diesterweg emphasized that the teacher should be an example for his students, worthy of emulation, “the personification of a mature, educated, if not perfect, then striving for perfection person” (33.203). In order for these requirements to be realized, the teacher must have a high level of general and special education and, at the same time, constantly improve his professional = pedagogical knowledge - one who himself is not developed, educated and educated. He is only able to actually educate and educate as long as he himself works on his own upbringing and education” (3,74).

Based on the principles he formulated, the nature of conformity (taking into account the age and individual characteristics and mental development of the child), the culture of conformity

(taking into account the conditions in which the child lives, national culture), amateur performance (the desire to develop children's creative activity), A. Diesterweg made demands on contemporary educators - to study "the nature of man in general and in particular, in order to faithfully serve its properties, features, aspirations" (3, 136).

Diesterweg attached great importance to such qualities of a teacher as independence of thought, activity and consistency of activity, determination, firmness of character and willpower.

Interest in the problem of the teacher's personality is also reflected in the works of many outstanding Russian educators and thinkers. Of particular note in this regard are the views and views of K.D. Ushinsky and L.N. Tolstoy.

The founder of Russian pedagogy K.D. Ushinsky insisted on the national specifics of education, on the need to take into account national national characteristics in its content, K.D. Ushinsky believed that "... education, created by the people themselves and based on folk principles, has that educational power that is not found in the best systems based on abstract ideas or borrowed from another people" (9. 161)). Ushinsky attached great importance to the role of the teacher, his personal and professional qualities in training and education, believing that "... no statutes and programs, no state body of an institution, no matter how cunningly invented, can replace the personality in the matter of education" (139, 63-64).

The teacher, in his opinion, should have a broad outlook, in-depth knowledge of his subject; knowledge in the field of philosophy, economics; knowledge reflecting the basic laws of human nature (anatomy, physiology, psychology, pedagogy). K.D. Ushinsky believed that a good teacher can only be successful if he constantly improves his knowledge and teaching skills.

The views of K.D. Ushinsky on the educational process were in many ways consonant with the views of representatives of humanistic pedagogy in Western Europe (Comenius, D. Diderot, I.G. Pestalozzi), in particular K.D. Ushinsky paid great attention to the educational function of education. K.D. Ushinsky argued that the teacher should not only teach, but at the same time educate, be a teacher-educator, "educate students with his subject" (139.66). Special attention to K.D. Ushinsky paid such a quality of a teacher as pedagogical tact, since he believed that a conscious and deliberate influence on a student is possible only with humane relations and friendly contacts.

A similar point of view was held by the founder of the theory of free education in Russia, L.N. Tolstoy. Recognizing the independent value of the personality of each child, his individual exclusivity, L.N. Tolstoy proposed to build such relations between the teacher and students, in which the child will be equal in rights with adults. Pro-testing against authoritarianism in the organization of the school educational process, L.N. Tolstoy noted that a new school would be created only when teachers abandoned "the old view of the school as a disciplined company of soldiers, commanded today by one lieutenant, tomorrow by another" (136,61).

L.N. Tolstoy made high moral and general cultural demands on the teacher. In his vision, a teacher is, first of all, a virtuous person who, by his personal example, influences the education of students. He considered one of the leading qualities of a teacher to be love for the profession and love for children. "If a teacher combines love for work and love for children, he is a perfect teacher" (136, 342) - wrote L.N. Tolstoy.

Thus, with all the difference in judgments and opinions at the turn of the XIX-XX centuries. in general terms, the requirements for the professional qualities of a teacher were formulated. It is necessary to name the main attributive qualities that, to one degree or another, were recognized

and reflected in pedagogical works by the end of the XIX century: the professional and pedagogical orientations of a person who devoted himself to school, his pedagogical “orientation”, as they began to say later; general education and culture; high moral and ethical qualities and properties; in-depth knowledge of one’s business, that is, competence in the field of a particular academic discipline; possession of teaching methods and, finally, awareness of the age characteristics of students.

The further movement of Russian, European and American scientific and pedagogical thought went, rather, in the direction of clarifying, developing and continuing the above postulates, rather than in the direction of their denial.

REFERENCES

1. Дистервег А. Избр. ред. соч. - Гос. Уч. пед, изд.-во, - Мин. проев. РСФСР, - М., 1956.- 374 с.
2. Жданов В.Ф. Артист музыкального театра: принципы формирования вокально-сценического мастерства. - М: Петит, 1996, - 293 с.
3. Кольшева ТА. Формирование у первокурсников интереса к профессии учителя музыки (на занятиях хорового класса муз,-пед. ф-та пединститутах Дисс... канд. пед. наук.-М- 1981. - 150 с.
4. Краевский В.В. Методология педагогического исследования: Пособие для педагога-исследователя. - Самара: Сам ГПИ, 1994. - 165 с.
5. Кузнецов Ю.М. Эмоции в хоровом исполнительстве, //В кн.: Художественный тип человека. Комплексные исследования, - М, 1994, - с. 146- 154.
6. Птица К.Б. О музыке и музыкантах: Сб. статей. - М.: Мистикос Логинов, 1994. - 437 с.
7. Работа хормейстера в детском хоре.// Сб. науч.- метод. статей./Под ред. Г,П. Стуловой. - М.: Прометей, 1992. – 246
8. Рубинштейн С.Л. Основы общей психологии. В 2-х т. Т.2. - М.: Педагогика, 1989. - 328 с. //Труды для чл. и чл.-кор. АПН СССР.